

Assessment of Information Needs and Information Seeking Pattern for Academic Activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East, Nigeria

^{*1}ADAMU, Abbas Lamido Gora (CLN) (abbasadamu@mau.edu.ng; +2348032095914).

²Professor DAWHA, E. M. K. (CLN) (emmanueldawha@gmail.com; +2348131592268).

³ Professor ABDULLAHI, Zainab Mohammed (CLN) (talk2zainabmautech@gmail.com; +2348036055067).

⁴Dr. UMAR, Babangida Babayi (CLN) (babayi@mau.edu.ng; +2347039389568).

^{1,3,4}Department of Library and Information Science, Modibbo Adama University, Yola.

²Department of Library and Information Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State.

^{*1}Corresponding Author.

Abstract

The study assessed information needs and information seeking pattern for academic activities among postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The study adopted a quantitative approach using a descriptive survey and the population of the study comprised of seven thousand eight hundred and sixty four (7,864) postgraduate students registered in 2024/2025 academic session in three (3) selected Federal Universities in North East, Nigeria. The universities were: Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU), Bauchi, Bauchi State, Modibbo Adama University (MAU), Yola, Adamawa State and University of Maiduguri (UNIMAID), Borno State. Two standadised questionnaire with 5-point Likert's scale were adapted and used as the research instrument. The questionnaire was validated and pilot test was carried out at Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State with Cronbach alpha of 0.85. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to analyse data generated from the two (2) research questions raised, while, inferential statistics of Pearson Product Momment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the two null-hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study showed that the level of information needs for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria was high. Also, the study indicated that the extent of information seeking pattern for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria was moderate. Furthermore, the study revealed that there is no significant influence between information needs and academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. Moreover, the study revealed that there is significant influence between information seeking pattern and academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria. The study concluded that while postgraduate students in federal universities in North East Nigeria exhibit strong awareness of their information needs, the effectiveness of their academic activities is more strongly shaped by their practical information seeking behaviours. Recommendations were made.

Keywords: Information Needs, Information Seeking Pattern, Academic activities, Postgraduate Students, Federal Universities, North East, Nigeria

Introduction

Universities have for centuries remain the apex of the educational system where human capital is developed for the sake of society and humanity. Universities as citadels of knowledge are established to promote excellence through teaching, learning, research, encourage innovation and creativity by producing high quality graduates with knowledge, exceptional skills and competencies which could build lifelong careers that contribute to the betterment of business and society. These can be achieved through rigorous, efficient and effective academic activities. Kansas State University (2023) defined academic activities to include physically attending a class where there is an opportunity for direct interaction between the instructor and students. The academic activities demand that the postgraduate student possess exceptional skills in order to explore information resources that could help them in their academic engagement. The skills and competencies include the ability to identify the need for information, adopt information seeking pattern, find, access, retrieve, evaluate and disseminate information for academic success. These skills are known as information literacy skills. Information needs refer to the recognition by individuals that they require information to bridge a gap in their knowledge in order to accomplish a task, solve a problem, or make a decision. Within universities, students' information needs are primarily driven by academic and research-related demands and are influenced by their level of study, discipline, and learning environment. University students' information needs arise from both formal academic activities and informal learning contexts. These needs are dynamic and vary according to level of study, discipline, and academic task.

The information seeking pattern of students in universities refers to the systematic and habitual ways through which students recognise and understand how information resources are organised, search for information, select sources, interact with information systems, and use the information obtained for academic and research purposes. It encompasses the processes, strategies, behaviours, and preferences students adopt when seeking information to support learning, problem-solving, and scholarly activities within the university environment. In university settings, students' information-seeking patterns typically involve a mix of formal and informal sources. However, despite the significance of information needs and information seeking pattern, several studies have reported either moderate or low level students especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Sahabi, et. al. (2021) revealed a generally high level of Information literacy, where the highest level of Information literacy was the ability to define the information needed in selected Federal University Libraries, North-West, Nigeria. Ekong and Ekong (2023) found that there is correlation between effective information literacy and academic performance of students but decried lack of reasonable ICT components in skills of information literacy in Nigerian schools. These studies as well as many others consulted by the researcher covered Southern Nigeria or other parts of Northern Nigeria, none focused on North East and most of the studies focused on undergraduate students, hence this study covered North East Nigeria, with a focus on postgraduate students. This is the gap that this study intended to cover to assess information needs and information seeking pattern for academic activities among postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Postgraduate students in universities are supposed to be the drivers of all innovations by possessing competencies required to navigate the ICT in their pursuit of activities. Their ability to identify information needs and information seeking patterns could enable them identify a gap in knowledge, employ the right search strategies to access relevant, quality and current information when conducting research and engaging in other academic activities seamlessly, thereby attaining academic excellence, achieve requirement for graduation as well as contributing to uplifting the ranking of their universities and developing their country in general. However, preliminary investigation conducted by the researcher revealed that, majority of postgraduate students in Federal Universities in North East Nigeria do not possess these competencies and have deficiencies in navigating through digital resources such as databases, e-journals and institutional repositories in searching for information to use when conducting research. This perhaps could be because majority of the students do not care to learn skills and competencies that could aid their academic activities, rather, they are more concerned about using smartphones, laptops etc. for entertainment, communicating, social networking as well as accessing the Internet for watching movies and playing games. Consequently, these deficiencies could lead to difficulty in pursuing academic activities, low academic performance as well as low quality research while writing thesis or dissertation. These and other factors formed the basis upon which this research assessed the information needs and information seeking pattern for academic activities among postgraduate students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to assess the:

1. level of information needs for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.
2. extent of information seeking pattern for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. what is the level of information needs for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria?
2. what is the extent of information seeking pattern for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null-hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant influence between information needs and academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence between information seeking pattern and academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Literature Review

Researchers and scholars have reported different findings on information literacy especially pertaining information needs and information seeking patterns of students. Sahabi, *et. al.* (2021) revealed a generally high level of Information literacy, where highest level of Information literacy was the ability to define the information needed, closely followed by the ability of selecting the information that is most appropriate to their needs, ability to use information to answer questions or solve problems, ability to identify different sources of information among others. In South-West, Nigeria, Adeniran and Onuoha (2022) revealed that the Information literacy level of respondents was high which were most skilled in the ‘ability to initiate how and where to find needed information; ability to locate information sources which ranked highest by the mean score rating and was followed by; ‘ability to select the information that is most appropriate to needs and ability to select search strategies by date, subject and language. In Tanzania, Mungwabi (2022) showed that the library’s information literacy instructions had moderate impact on most of the respondents’ capacity to express and find what information resources they need, how to use the information ethically and how to evaluate online information credibly.

Furthermore, Tachie-Donkor and Ezema (2023) clearly demonstrated some level of competency in ‘Information Seeking Strategies. Adekunle and Madukoma (2022) reported that the information literacy competence level of doctoral students in universities in Ogun State is adjudged high particularly on information search subconstruct, finding electronic sources of information (Library OPACs, e-databases, e-journals, etc.) knowing information-search strategies (descriptors, Boolean operators, etc.) and searching for and retrieving internet information (advanced searches, directories). In North Central Nigeria, Fajonyomi, Bukar and Ambali (2021) indicated that majority of students agree that they had a high level of Information literacy especially on information seeking pattern, which showed that the respondents had a high level of information seeking pattern. Oyewusi and Bamigbade (2021) uncovered a compelling connection between students' information literacy regarding the ability to identify information needs and their academic achievements, indicating that individuals with robust information literacy competences tended to exhibit higher levels of critical thinking and research prowess, thereby translating into superior academic performance. Adedoyin and Oyelekan (2021) unveiled a significant positive association between information literacy competences and academic success, highlighting the pivotal role of information literacy in enhancing students' ability to excel in their academic pursuits. Akinade and Ogunyade (2024) found a significant relationship between postgraduate students’ information-seeking behaviour and their research effectiveness in Nigerian universities. Popoola (2021) study reported that effective information-seeking skills significantly enhance academic performance and research productivity among postgraduate students.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative approach using a descriptive survey. The population for the study comprised of seven thousand eight hundred and sixty four (7,864) postgraduate students registered in 2024/2025 session in three (3) selected Federal Universities in North East, Nigeria. The universities were: Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU), Bauchi, Bauchi State, Modibbo Adama University (MAU), Yola, Adamawa State and University of Maiduguri (UNIMAID),

Borno State. Research Advisors (2006) published table in which confidence level of 95% with the margin error of ±2.5 was used to select 365 respondents which represented the sample for the study. Multistage sampling technique was used to cluster samples for the study. The study adapted two standardised research instruments to cover the two (2) independent variables (information literacy and digital competencies), which are the Society for College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL) which introduced seven pillars of Information literacy (2015) and Digital Competence Framework 2.1 of EU Science Hub (DIGCOMP) (2018). The instrument was validated and pilot test was conducted at Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State, with a total average of 0.85 reliability coefficient. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to analyse data generated from the two (2) research questions raised, while, inferential statistics of Pearson Chi Square was used to test the two null-hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis and Results

Three hundred and sixty-five (365) copies of the questionnaire were administered on postgraduate students in three (3) universities selected in North Eastern Nigeria, out of which, two hundred and ninety-seven (297) (81.7%) copies were properly filled, retrieved and found useable.

Research Question One: What is the level of information needs for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the level of information needs for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Table with 6 columns: S/N, Items, N, Mean, Std., Dec. It contains 8 rows of data and a final row for Cluster Mean.

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 1 presents the responses on the level of information needs for academic activities. The respondents expressed very high level on only one (1) item, which is the “ability to sense when there is deficiency in knowledge and needed information” which attracts the highest mean score of (X̄ = 4.25, SD = 0.52). Similarly, the respondents expressed high level in five (5) items listed, which include: “the ability to identify the types of information that best meet their information need for research and assignments” (X̄ = 4.13, SD = 0.56); “the ability to identify terms to be used for searching information” (X̄ = 4.03, SD = 0.57); “the skills to articulate current knowledge on a topic” (X̄ = 3.83, SD = 0.68); “the ability to define concepts of a topic” (X̄ = 3.63, SD = 0.62); and “the ability to manage time effectively to complete a search” (X̄ = 3.57, SD = 0.62). Meanwhile, the overall weighted mean score of X̄ = 3.76, SD = 0.61 was obtained, indicating that the level of information needs for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria was high. The high proportion of the information needs underscores the practical importance of fostering information identification skills to enhance academic performance and engagement. This finding is in consonance with the study of Sahabi, et. al. (2021) which revealed a generally high level of Information literacy, where highest level of Information literacy was the ability to define the information needed, closely followed by the ability of selecting the information that is most appropriate to their needs, ability to use information to answer questions or solve problems, ability to identify different sources of information among others. Similarly, Adeniran and Onuoha (2022) revealed that the Information literacy level of respondents was high which were most skilled in the ‘ability to initiate how and where to find needed information; ability to locate information sources which ranked highest by the mean score rating and was followed by; ‘ability to select the information that is most appropriate to needs and ability to select search strategies by date, subject and language. While, Mungwabi (2022) disagrees with this finding and reported a moderate level on most of the respondents’ capacity to express and find what information resources they need, how to use the information ethically and how to evaluate online information credibly.

Research Question Two: What is the extent of information seeking pattern for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on the extent of information seeking pattern for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	Std.	Dec.
1	I have the ability to understand how information resources are organised digitally	297	3.95	0.46	HL
2	I understand how to search information using various search terms such as author, title and subject	297	2.79	0.63	ML
3	I know how libraries provide access to the information resources using the library catalogue and other information retrieval tools	297	3.02	0.59	ML
4	I have the ability of locating the information needed using different search engines	297	3.64	0.49	HL

5	I have the knowledge of how digital technologies are providing collaborative tools to create and share information	297	3.36	0.51	ML
6	I can make complex search strategies and also make a difference to the breadth and depth of information found	297	2.34	0.64	LL
7	I have the ability to limit search strategies by subject, language and date	297	2.01	0.67	LL
8	I can search for information even from unfamiliar sources and make academic decisions	297	3.77	0.48	HL
Cluster Mean		297	3.11	0.57	ML

Source: Field Work (2025)

Table 2 presents the responses on the extent of information seeking pattern for academic activities. The respondents expressed high level on three (3) items. They include: “the ability to understand how information resources are organised digitally” ($\bar{X} = 3.95$, $SD = 0.46$); “the ability to search for information even from unfamiliar sources and make academic decisions” ($\bar{X} = 3.77$, $SD = 0.48$) and “the ability of locating the information needed using different search engines” ($\bar{X} = 3.64$, $SD = 0.49$). The respondents further expressed moderate level on three (3) items listed such as: “the knowledge of how digital technologies are providing collaborative tools to create and share information” ($\bar{X} = 3.36$, $SD = 0.51$); “how libraries provide access to the information resources using the library catalogue and other information retrieval tools” ($\bar{X} = 3.02$, $SD = 0.59$) and “understand how to search information using various search terms such as author, title and subject” ($\bar{X} = 2.79$, $SD = 0.63$). Meanwhile, the overall weighted mean score of $\bar{X} = 3.11$, $SD = 0.57$ was obtained, indicating that the extent of information seeking pattern for academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria was moderate. In conformity with this finding, Tachie-Donkor and Ezema (2023) revealed that students from the College of Education Studies, University of Cape Coast, Ghana clearly demonstrated some level of competency in ‘Information Seeking Strategies. In addition, Issa, Amusan, and Daura (2021) revealed that Nigerian postgraduate students possess moderate information literacy skills, particularly in the use of search engines and digital resources. In disagreement, Adekunle and Madukoma (2022) reported that the information literacy competence level of doctoral students in universities in Ogun State is adjudged high. Fajonyomi, Bukar and Ambali (2021) indicated that majority of students agree that they had a high level of Information literacy especially on information seeking pattern, which showed that the respondents had a high level of information seeking pattern.

Hypothesis Testing

H01: There is no significant influence between information needs and academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi-Square Result on significant influence between information needs and academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria

Table with 4 columns: Chi-Square Tests, Value, Df, Asymptotic Significance (2-sided). Rows include Pearson Chi-Square, Likelihood Ratio, Linear-by-Linear Association, and N of Valid Cases.

Source: Field Work (2026)

Table 3 presents the Chi-Square result on significant influence between information needs and academic activities. The result indicated a Pearson Chi Square of 282.310a, Degree of freedom(df) = 323 and p-value (Asymptotic Significance, 2-sided) = 0.950.

H02: There is no significant influence between information seeking pattern and academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-Square Result on significant influence between information seeking pattern and academic activities among Postgraduate Students in Federal Universities, North East Nigeria

Table with 4 columns: Chi-Square Tests, Value, Df, Asymptotic Significance (2-sided). Rows include Pearson Chi-Square, Likelihood Ratio, Linear-by-Linear Association, and N of Valid Cases.

Source: Field Work (2026)

Table 4 presents the Chi-Square result on significant influence between information seeking pattern and academic. The result indicated a Pearson Chi Square of 356.431a, Degree of freedom (df) = 357 and p-value (Asymptotic Significance, 2-sided) = 0.499.

Universities, North East Nigeria. In corroborating with this finding, Akinade and Ogunyade (2024) found a significant relationship between postgraduate students' information-seeking behaviour and their research effectiveness in Nigerian universities. Similarly, Popoola (2021) reported that effective information-seeking skills significantly enhance academic performance and research productivity among postgraduate students.

Conclusion

This study examined information needs and information seeking patterns for academic activities among postgraduate students in federal universities in North East Nigeria. The findings revealed that postgraduate students demonstrated a high level of information needs in relation to their academic activities. However, the extent of students' information seeking patterns was found to be moderate. Although they showed familiarity with how digital information resources are organised and demonstrated the ability to search for information from unfamiliar sources using various search engines, their overall approach to seeking information was not highly advanced. Furthermore, the study established that there was no significant influence between information needs and academic activities. In contrast, a significant influence was found between information seeking patterns and academic activities. This indicates that how students search for, access, and utilise information plays a more decisive role in enhancing their academic work than simply acknowledging their information needs. Overall, the study concludes that, while postgraduate students in federal universities in North East Nigeria exhibit strong awareness of their information needs, the effectiveness of their academic activities is more strongly shaped by their practical information seeking behaviours. Strengthening students' strategic information seeking skills may therefore yield greater improvements in their academic engagement and productivity.

Recommendation

Based on these findings, the study recommended the following:

1. Enhancing information need identification skills: University libraries should collaborate with academic departments to provide targeted information literacy instruction focusing on recognising knowledge gaps and translating research problems into searchable concepts.
2. Developing effective information seeking patterns: Continuous orientation programmes by university libraries should be organised to familiarise postgraduate students with the structure and organisation of digital information systems.

References

- Adedoyin, O. B., & Oyelekan, O. (2021). Information literacy and Undergraduate Students' Academic Performance in Nigerian Private Universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4995/>
- Adekunle, A. & Madukoma, E. (2022). An Assessment of Information literacy Competence of Doctoral Students in Universities in Ogun State. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7172. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7172>.
- Adeniran, P. O. & Onuoha, U. D. (2022). Influence of Information literacy on Postgraduate Students' Use of Electronic Resources in Private University Libraries in South-West, Nigeria. *Communications and Network*, 10: 164-179. <http://www.scirp.org/journal/cn>.

- Adeoye, A. A. & Adeoye, B. J. (2021). Digital literacy of undergraduate students in universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved from: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1665>
- Akinade, O. J., & Ogunyade, T. O. (2024). Information-seeking behaviour of undergraduate students in Nigerian universities. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 12(3), 45–55.
- Ekong, U. O. & Ekong, V. E. (2023). Impact of Information literacy on the use of e-resources among tertiary institution in Akwa Ibom Nigeria. *Journal of Technology* 37(2):423-431.
- Fajonyomi, O. J., Bukar, S. S. & Ambali, Z. O. (2021). Information literacy and Use of Library Resources by Postgraduate Students in University of Ilorin. *International Journal of Library and Information Technology (IJLIT)*, 1(1): 66 – 77.
- Issa, A. O., Amusan, B. B., & Daura, U. D. (2021). Information literacy skills and use of electronic resources by postgraduate students in Nigerian universities. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 9(2), 45–56.
- Kansas State University (2023). Definition of Academic Related Activity. <https://www.k-state.edu/registrar/students/academicpolicy/academic-activity.html>.
- Lawal, A. M., & Garba, S. K. (2020). Information literacy competencies of postgraduate students in selected Nigerian universities. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 12(4), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.5897/IJLIS2020.0956>.
- Mungwabi, H. N. (2022). The effectiveness of library information literacy instructions given to undergraduate students at the University of Dar es Salaam. *University of Dar es Salaam Library Journal*, 14(2); 99-112.
- Popoola, S. O. (2021). The use of information sources and services and its effect on the research output of social scientists in Nigerian universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1–10. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/183>.
- Sahabi, M. K., Efe, O. E. & Bukar, S. S. (2021). Information literacy as a Factor Influencing Use of Electronic Information Resources by Undergraduate Students in Selected Federal University Libraries, North-West, Nigeria. *International Journal of Management, Social Sciences, Peace and Conflict Studies (IJMSSPCS)*, 4(4): 145 – 154.
- Tachie-Donkor, G. & Ezema, I. J. (2023). Effect of Information literacy on university students' information seeking behaviour and lifelong learning. *Heliyon*, e18427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18427>.